

***D1.1: Conceptual framework for food
loss and waste***

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List of Abbreviations used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
EPA	(United States) Environmental Protection Agency
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization (of the United Nations)
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FSC	Food Supply Chain
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
ICT	Information & Communication Technology
LCA	Life Cycle Assessments
MES	Manufacturing Execution System
QC/QA	Quality Assurance / Quality Control
SFSC	Short Food Supply Chain
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Lab
UNEP	UN Environment Programme
WP	Work package
WRAP	Waste & Resources Action Programme

Executive Summary

This report is the first deliverable of WP1. In it, we provide a conceptual framework for food loss and waste (FLW). This framework is meant to establish a collective understanding of what is and what is not considered FLW, as well as provide an overview of the food system actors and dynamics behind FLW and possible interventions to reduce or reuse FLW. The discussion of interventions also details the specific interventions that are studied within the Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) included in the ZEROW project.

This framework paves the way for the development of an economic model that can process meso- and macro-economic scenarios for FLW, both top-down at European Union (EU) level, but also bottom-up based on upscaling scenarios of the nine ZEROW Systemic Innovations Living Labs (SILLs). The latter will later be discussed in deliverable D1.2 (FLW economic model development & SILL-based validation), while the former will be covered in D1.3 (Modelling the impact of FLW interventions at meso- (food sector) and macro- (EU) levels).

A fundamental element of the framework is the definition of FLW. We start from the EU definition of FLW but propose a number of refinements that enrich the conceptual framework that is developed in this report. Examples are the use of natural resources, identifying pre-harvest losses, and considering the nutritional values of produced (and wasted) food.

The main elements of the conceptual framework are the various food supply chain actors. In chapter 3, we discuss the role in reducing FLW of, respectively, primary producers, logistics service providers, processors, wholesalers, retail, foodservice, consumers, and society. In the following chapter, for each of these actors, the specific sources, and drivers for FLW are listed.

Given the sources of FLW, chapter 5 lists the potential interventions to reduce it. Existing interventions are discussed based on a literature review, and ample attention is given to the interventions that are proposed by the ZEROW SILLs. Then, the basic conceptual framework for FLW from the academic literature is enriched in such a way that the success or failure of these interventions can be measured. The updated conceptual framework is summarised in the following picture:

The report ends with some high-level conclusions and recommendations for the remainder of the ZEROW project and, in particular, for the future development of the conceptual framework.

1 Introduction

1.1 ZEROW project summary

Figure 1 presents ZEROW project in a nutshell.

Figure 1 ZEROW at a glance

The ZEROW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2 ZEROW approach

To reach its goals, ZEROW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks, and deliverables.

1.2 Deliverable 1.1 aims

This report is the first deliverable of WP1. In this report, we aim to provide a conceptual framework for food loss and waste (FLW). This framework is meant to establish a collective understanding of what is and what is not considered FLW, as well as provide an overview of the food system actors and dynamics behind FLW and possible interventions to reduce or reuse FLW. The discussion of interventions also details the specific interventions studied within the Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) included in the ZEROW project.

1.3 Mapping ZEROW outputs

The purpose of this chapter is to map ZEROW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2 Adherence to ZEROW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Outline	Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE D1.1		
FLW conceptual model – Will provide a conceptual model for the FLW economic effects. (Page 12 of DoW)	Chapter 6	Chapter 6 synthesizes the inventory made in the preceding chapters to arrive at a proposed model that is suitable for macro-economic modelling and captures the most important aspects of the ZEROW SILLs.
TASK T1.1 FLW conceptual model		
In this Task, we will determine the boundaries [C1] of the generic food supply chain with which we will work. The supply chain will commence from consumers, consuming food at home or away from home. Processors, retailers, foodservice (i.e., hotels, restaurants & institutions) will represent the middle parts of the supply chain. At the upstream side of the food supply chain will be the farmers; we will consider both their decisions with respect to the downstream actors as well as ways to reduce pre-harvest losses. The conceptual model will also include ways of valorising (e.g., donations) and disposing of food waste (e.g., landfill/incineration, land/sewage [C2]. The findings of the literature review [C3] and our exchange with Living Labs will be used to build the theoretical economic model. (Page 11 of DoW) [C4]	[C1] Chapter 3 [C2] Chapters 2 and 5 [C3] Relevant literature is surveyed throughout the document, directly where applicable. [C4] Chapter 5, and further developed in D1.2 and D1.3	Chapter 3 discusses the actor types that are identified in the conceptual model, from farmers until consumers. The measures that can be taken by these actors are discussed in chapter 5, where we discriminate between generic interventions and interventions that are in scope of the ZEROW SILLs. Chapter 2 covers possible ways of valorising and disposing of waste, structured in a FLW hierarchy. The proposed conceptual model will be used to scope the economic model, which will be developed and evaluated in T1.2 and T1.3.

1.4 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In this section, we describe how the report is related within ZEROW to some other deliverables, and we outline the structure of the remainder of the report.

1.4.1 Links with other ZEROW deliverables

This report aims to pave the way for developing an economic model that can process meso- and macro-economic scenarios for FLW, both top-down at EU level and bottom-up based on upscaling scenarios of the nine ZEROW Systemic Innovations Living Labs (SILLs). The latter will later be discussed in deliverable **D1.2** (FLW economic model development & SILL-based validation), while the former will be covered in **D1.3** (Modelling the impact of FLW interventions at meso- (food sector) and macro- (EU) levels).

Furthermore, when developing this report, we collaborated closely with the main authors of **D4.1** on Systemic Innovation maturity gaps, in particular relating to the definition of FLW, and remarks related to its scope. Another element of D4.1 that is of importance for our report is the interaction (and possible conflict) between FLW reduction, food poverty, and food security, as this, for example, calls for the inclusion of food banks in our conceptual model.

On the topic of engagement with initiatives outside the ZEROW project, there is a link of our work with **D9.1** (Action plan for liaison & stakeholder engagement), as in our report we have included descriptions of recent and current EU projects that have provided important insights for the development of an economic model for FLW.

And finally, of course, there is a direct link between our report and all nine SILLs in ZEROW. The leaders of all SILLs have been interviewed to make sure that we fully understand the scope and plan of the initiatives. This ensures that our conceptual model will indeed be suitable to model all ZEROW interventions evaluated in the SILLs as described in **D4.3** (SILL strategic plans).

1.4.2 Outline of the report

This report is further organized as follows. In **Chapter 2**, we will formulate and reflect on the definition of FLW to be used in our conceptual model. We will also establish the boundaries of our analysis and discuss which elements will be taken up by the two subsequent deliverables of work package (WP) 1. Then in **Chapter 3**, the food system will be discussed focussing on the actors, from farmers to consumers, and their interactions. Once the food system is established for this report, we turn to the role of FLW in **Chapter 4**, where we discuss its sources and drivers. The aim of the ZEROW project is to reduce this FLW quantity in the EU, so in **Chapter 5** we discuss many ways of intervening. We separately describe interventions found in the literature (Section 5.1) and interventions evaluated in our ZEROW project (Section 5.2). Chapters 1-5 have delivered all necessary information for our FLW conceptual model, which is formulated in **Chapter 6**. Finally, in **Chapter 7**, we conclude and provide recommendations to be taken up by the ZEROW consortium, practitioners, and policy makers.

2 Food loss and waste – Definitions and scope

2.1 The relevance of food loss and waste

The production and distribution of food are one of the main contributors to climate change, as it accounts for over a quarter of global greenhouse emissions (Poore and Nemecek 2018). It is, therefore, even more worrying that a lot of the food that is produced never makes it to consumption; it is widely reported (e.g. Gustavsson et al. 2011) that a third of the globally produced food mass is lost or wasted. Considering that the global population is expected to increase significantly in size, this problem will only get bigger and more relevant.

In addition to the environmental perspective, Food Loss and Waste (FLW) also has significant economic and social implications. Today, a significant share of the population does not have sufficient access to food: almost 10% of the population is considered undernourished (FAO 2021). To provide food for the growing world population, reducing the percentage of produced food that results in waste would clearly contribute.

Because of the above, the reduction of FLW is also high on the agenda of policy makers. For instance, in 2023, the European Commission aims to introduce legally binding targets to reduce food waste (European Commission 2022).

Reducing FLW is a means to an end: to reduce CO₂ emissions, limit the environmental/resource degradation and improve food security (Drabik, de Gorter, and Reynolds 2019). Reducing food waste, however, offers multiple benefits for people and the planet, contributing to improving food security, cutting pollution, saving money, reducing the pressures on nature and climate, and creating opportunities for the economy and society. It is for this reason that the UN's Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12.3 sets a clear target of halving per capita global food waste by retailers and consumers by 2030 (UNEP DTU Partnership 2021).

From a global perspective, FLW reductions improve both food security and the environment – if less food gets lost, less needs to be produced to improve global food security thus also reducing environmental impacts. It, however, also implies redistribution creating winners and losers - which are unlikely to be compensated - along the supply chain. For example, FL reduction in processing reduces demand for primary products, decreasing rural wage labourers and food producers' incomes (Kuiper and Cui 2021).

The link between food waste with SDG2 of Zero Hunger is perhaps most apparent. Today, an estimated 700 million people are food insecure, which means that they cannot rely on having a decent meal every day and regularly go to bed hungry (FAO, 2022), and this number is rising as can be seen in Figure 3 below.

Kummu et al. (2012) summarize the impact of FLW on a global scale:

- Around 1/4 of the produced food (in terms of kcal) is lost in the FSC.
- 23–24% of the total use of water, cropland and fertilisers are used to produce losses.
- Around half of the losses could be prevented with a more efficient supply chain.
- One billion extra people could be fed if food crop losses could be halved.

FIGURE 1 THE NUMBER OF UNDERNOURISHED PEOPLE IN THE WORLD CONTINUED TO RISE IN 2020. BETWEEN 720 AND 811 MILLION PEOPLE IN THE WORLD FACED HUNGER IN 2020. CONSIDERING THE MIDDLE OF THE PROJECTED RANGE (768 MILLION), 118 MILLION MORE PEOPLE WERE FACING HUNGER IN 2020 THAN IN 2019 – OR AS MANY AS 161 MILLION, CONSIDERING THE UPPER BOUND OF THE RANGE

Figure 3. Food insecurity trend (FAO 2021)

At the same time, as mentioned earlier, globally about a third (of all food biomass that is produced for human consumption is wasted or used for other purposes than intended. This amounts to 1.3 billion tons of food per year. Related to the number of undernourished people in Figure 1, this is more than 2 tons per undernourished person. Many interventions to reduce this food waste have been proposed and evaluated and will be summarized in chapter 4.

It can be argued that reducing FLW can have a beneficial effect on food security. After all, the natural resources that are needed to produce food, which, especially in the developed world, is discarded for a significant percentage, can be used to feed people who are acutely food insecure. Reduction of FLW could contribute to an increase in the productivity of food production advocated for in the Zero Hunger SDG. On the other hand, if FLW that is currently redistributed to people that are food insecure would be prevented from occurring at all, such FLW prevention initiatives might have unintended negative side effects for food security.

It is widely acknowledged that the earth can carry a maximum number of about 9-10 billion people based on its natural resources and technologies (Lipinski et al. 2016). This is what is called the planetary boundary. Today, the world population is around 7.5 billion people. Therefore, on a simplified and aggregated level, there is enough food for everybody. This significantly changes when a third of food biomass does not find its way to human consumption. Feeding the world population and avoiding hunger is thus a matter of efficient and effective food supply chains, and a fair allocation of resources and food.

To be on track towards the attainment of the UN Sustainable Development Goal, EU Member States have agreed on an indicative Union-wide food waste reduction target of 30% by 2025 and 50% by 2030 (EU, 2018). To map the most promising interventions to achieve this goal, in the next chapter, we dive deeper into the sources and drivers for FLW in the various stages of the FSC.

2.2 What is considered food loss and waste?

The terms food loss and food waste are both used to describe food that does not end up making it to the intended human consumption. The two terms are, however, sometimes used interchangeably, and sometimes they are used to point to different things. To clarify, we briefly discuss two of the leading definitions that have been used: one by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), and one by the European Commission. A more elaborate discussion on the definition of food loss and waste is available in Deliverable D4.1 of our ZEROW project.

A key difference between the FAO definition and the EC definition is that FAO distinguishes between food loss and food waste, whereas the EU only refers to food waste. FAO refers to food loss as “the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by food suppliers in the chain, excluding retailers, foodservice providers and consumers” (FAO 2022a) and to food waste as “the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by food suppliers in the chain, including retailers, foodservice providers and consumers” (FAO 2022b). Basically, loss is used in the initial stages of the supply chain, and waste is used in the later stages. In the overview of the food supply chain shown in Figure 1, this distinction is also illustrated. As can be seen, both the FAO and EU perspective start at primary production, after products are harvested up to the point of consumption.

ZEROW will use the EU definition of FLW within SILLs and WPs as a starting point for its work. However, we will not ignore FLW streams that fall outside of its scope. At a later stage in our project, our results might also lead to recommendations with regards to changes to the EU definition of FLW.

Figure 4 Overview of the various stages of the FSC and related food loss and waste terminology (based on (Akkerman, Farahani, and Grunow 2010)).

The EU instead uses food waste to refer to all waste streams throughout the supply chain (as also shown in Figure 1). Formally, the EU, in its waste directive, simply defines food waste as all food that has become waste (EU 2018). Here, it refers to the Food Law to define food as “any substance or product, whether processed, partially processed or unprocessed, intended to be, or reasonably expected to be ingested by humans” (EU 2002).

2.3 Discussion of food loss and waste definitions

Even though the definitions of FLW seem relatively straightforward in terms of what is considered FLW, the definitions also make clear what is **not** considered when FLW gets measured. Furthermore, as the purpose of the definition is to indicate what is covered when we talk about FLW, it does not distinguish between different type or waste or what happens to it. And the scope of these kind of definitions is important: what is not (officially) measured is a lot less likely to be addressed. Also, national or international policies to reduce FLW will only relate to what is within the definitions.

In this section, we briefly discuss the three main challenges that this leads to:

- Pre-harvest losses are not considered part of FLW, so the question is where the scope of an FLW definition should start?
- Consumer losses are only considered in a relatively simplistic manner, so the question is where the scope of an FLW definition should end?
- Potential valorisation of FLW in the food supply chain is not considered, so the question is whether it should matter what happens to FLW.

In Figure 1, these three categories have also been included in relation to the various stages of the food supply chain.

At the beginning of the food supply chain, the EU definition only considers food products to possibly become FLW (and thus included in the measurement of FLW) after harvesting. This, for instance, means that products that remain on the field are not considered FLW (and here considered pre-harvest losses, as did not make it to harvest). As discussed later in Chapter 4, FLW in primary production is often the result of economic incentives or high visual product quality standards, but the scope of FLW definitions is such that the impact of these FLW drivers might not be captured in the measures we use to address FLW.

Throughout the supply chain, many FLW streams are valorised in one way or another, for instance, in energy production by anaerobic digestion, as an ingredient in the production of animal feed, or as donations to food banks that might still be able to repurpose towards human consumption. Figure 2 illustrates the hierarchy of valorisation options that is also recognized in EU policy. A similar hierarchy has been introduced in the US by the EPA, based on: (1) source reduction, (2) feed hungry people, (3) feed animals, (4) industrial uses, and (5) composting (EPA 2022).

Figure 2: Food waste hierarchy including selected potential interventions (Papargyropoulou et al. 2014), adapted from EU policies)

Using such hierarchies and prioritisations makes clear that there are different things we can do with FLW and that it matters which one we use, as higher levels of valorisation are preferable. In most cases, this is also a good proxy for the best use in terms of the underlying environmental impacts. However, if FLW is not used for human consumption, it is still considered FLW in any definition or related waste measurement effort. This means that interventions to reuse FLW might have large positive environmental impacts, but that it is often not captured in FLW measures. This prevents the efficient reuse of FLW streams, see also Teigiserova, Hamelin, and Thomsen (2020).

At the end of the supply chain, the definition of FLW also becomes more difficult. When considering the efficient and effective use of food, discarded food at the consumer level is clearly important and considered within the scope of the FLW definitions. However, in many parts of the world, overconsumption is a significant driver of health problems such as obesity. Dietary choices, therefore, have negative side effects if nutrient intakes go beyond the recommended levels. However, overconsumption of food would not be considered food waste. Also, when considering the underlying environmental impacts, there is currently no differentiation between dietary choices consisting of many food products with high environmental impacts or low environmental impacts. There is no direct connection between FLW and the abovementioned health issues, but food consumption choices and behaviour are considered drivers of FLW, and how and where to end the scope of FLW is then also not straightforward,

Finally, beyond the discussion of what is included in the definition of FLW, is the discussion about how to measure FLW. Current measurements are mostly considering FLW quantities. It is important to realize that this is not always a good representation of the underlying environmental impact of food waste or a useful way to identify how to address food insecurity. For instance, wasting a kilogram of beef is significantly more harmful to the environment than wasting a kilogram of apples. And to complicate this even further, wasting these same apples in various stages in the supply chain leads to different environmental impacts, as additional logistics activities and packaging material will have been involved.

Similarly, in terms of food security, reducing waste of products with different nutritional profiles leads to the same food waste reduction measure, but clearly differs a lot in terms of possible reduction in food insecurity.

2.4 Food loss and waste – scope of this report

In the remainder of this report, we will use a broad perspective on FLW. We do not explicitly exclude pre-harvest losses, broader views on consumer losses, or discussions about valorisation options that do not lead to human consumption. This allows us to provide a comprehensive overview of the issues around FLW, including for example its underlying environmental impacts. It also allows a broader discussion of FLW sources and drivers, and it can inform a wider range of interventions aiming to reduce or reuse FLW.

3 Supply chain actors and interactions

A crucial step in developing a conceptual framework for food loss and waste is the identification of the most relevant supply chain actors and their interactions. For this identification we base ourselves on academic literature as much as possible. In this chapter, we will discuss the specifics of each actor type concerning FLW. The description is largely based on insights from recent academic literature. Luo, Olsen, and Liu (2021) already observed that in the light of the development towards a circular economy and sustainable FSCs, research on FLW reduction and prevention had drawn much attention from academia, practitioners, and governments. The significance of FLW has been highlighted in the literature due to its impact on society, economy, and the environment. The scale of this impact is considerable. Corrado and Sala (2018) state that FLW quantities range between 194–389 kg per person per year on the global scale, and between 158–298 kg per person per year on the European scale.

Stenmarck et al. (2016) attribute these waste figures to individual segments of the FSC (see Figure 5). They conclude, based on survey data of 2012 and reconfirmed by Caldeira, De Laurentiis, and Sala (2019), that the sectors contributing most to FLW are households and processing. These two sectors account for 72 percent of EU food waste, although there is considerable uncertainty around the estimate for the processing sector compared to all the other sectors. Of the remaining 28 percent of food waste, 11 million tonnes (12%) come from Foodservice, 9 million tonnes (10%) come from primary production and 5 million tonnes (5%) come from wholesale and retail.

Figure 5 Split of EU-28 food waste in 2012 by sector; includes food and inedible parts associated with food (Stenmarck et al. 2016)

Although a lot can be found in the academic literature about (conceptual models for) FLW already, it is worthwhile to develop an enhanced model for the specific purpose of our ZEROW project. Although existing frameworks provide a useful starting point, not all our package goals can be achieved by using them. This is because the two main goals of WP1 are, on the one hand, to model the impact that the specific SILLs (WP4) will achieve and, on the other hand, to estimate the possible impact if these SILLs were to be scaled up to European level.

In this chapter, we will discuss the existing frameworks and the actors that are most modelled. Then, in chapter 4 we will describe the sources and drivers for FLW and in chapter 5 we will discuss all SILLs and their requirements for the conceptual framework. In chapter 6, we combine these insights to arrive at our proposed ZEROW conceptual framework.

In the next subsections, we will discuss the main actors of the FSC one by one. Xue et al. (2017) observed an unbalanced coverage in the literature of the FSC with a focus on retail and consumer waste. Taking note of this, we strive to discuss every element of the food system in similar detail. We start with a discussion of the overall systems and then consecutively address primary producers, distributors, processors, wholesalers, retailers, foodservice companies, and consumers. We end the discussion by reflecting on how society at large is impacted by FLW and vice versa.

3.1 Food system

In recent years, more attention has been given to the entire food system, rather than focussing on interventions on a single level of the FSC. Food system frameworks are increasingly used to enhance our understanding of the interactions between agriculture, food security and nutrition. This is needed to shape policies of governments and design strategic interventions by companies to reduce FLW and improve sustainability in the broad sense. Food system thinking links such steps as production, processing, distribution, preparation, and consumption of food, with elements of the environment, people, inputs, infrastructure, and institutions (Borman et al. 2022). Finally, Campoy-Muñoz et al. (2021) also stress the importance of considering the whole supply chain instead of focusing only on reducing the waste at consumers, which seems to be the approach taken by most industrialized countries.

Individual phases of the FSC are summarized by quite a few authors already. Figure 4 in the previous chapter summarized the approach of Akkerman, Farahani, and Grunow (2010). One notable addition of their model is that they discriminate between retail and foodservice as preceding stages before the consumer.

Garrone, Melacini, and Perego (2014) finetuned this model by identifying multiple segments within these stages, see Table 3.

Table 3. Segmentation of supply chain stages (Garrone, Melacini, and Perego 2014). Note that in since this publication, new initiatives have appeared such as cloud kitchens, meal kits, personalised nutrition, home delivery, etc.

Food supply chain stage	Segments
Primary production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fruit and vegetables • Cereals • Livestock farming • Fishing
Manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambient • Chilled • Frozen
Retail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution centres • Points of sale
Food service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collective catering • Commercial catering

A recent conceptualization was provided by de Gorter et al. (2021a), who further disconnected food consumption at home and in hotels, restaurants and institutions. This makes sense since it is to be expected that FLW interventions at foodservice locations strongly differ from interventions focusing on food waste in household kitchens. The economic model developed by Gorter et al. (2021a), see Figure 6, is used to show that “an exogenous reduction in the waste rate has both a direct quantity impact on how much of the purchased food can be consumed and an indirect quantity impact through the demand elasticity since lower waste rates reduce the effective unit price of food consumed.”

Figure 6. FLW Conceptual framework (de Gorter et al. 2021b)

The two above models identify the main actors in a typical FSC and analyse them in a subsequent chain-like manner, which for example creates the simplification that transport and handling is only modelled after production and for example not after processors or retailers. The next point is to discuss how these supply chains can operate effectively through system-wide cooperation that benefits all stakeholders involved (Bhattacharya and Fayezi 2021). In their review paper, Wang, Yuan, and Tang (2021) stress the importance of feedback loops in the system to achieve circularity. Traditional linear pathways do not suffice to reduce FLW, ensure recycling, enhance food security, and achieve environmental sustainability. The role of FLW in the circular economy is further discussed by Oliveira, Lago, and Dal' Magro (2021).

Figure 7 provides a visual combination of the linear and circular interpretations of the FSC.

Figure 7. Circular and linear representation of the FSC (Wang, Yuan, and Tang 2021)

Lemaire and Limbourg (2019) provide an overview of the literature on system-wide FLW reduction interventions and categorize them under the following topics:

- Awareness raising and consumer education
- Global coordination and information sharing
- Sustainable supply chains
- Standards and specification in product design
- Shift in responsibility
- Logistics network design
- Inventory management models and lot sizing
- Packaging and conservation means
- Redistribution
- Food waste recovery and disposal

One of the key aspects of food system-wide interventions is collaboration, the second bullet in the list above. This is confirmed by Arias Bustos and Moors (2018). They state that although collaboration and exchange of information have been suggested to be one of the most important means of reducing food losses and waste along the FSC, the absence of information and/or the reticence of actors to exchange information is still one of the most challenging structural inefficiencies along FSC.

In the next sections, we leave the system approach and will look in detail at the role of individual FSC actors in FLW. It is important to study these actors in close connection with each other. An integrated multi-sectoral approach across the whole FSC is required to address global challenges such as food and nutrition insecurity (Augustin et al. 2016).

3.2 Primary production

The start of a typical FSC is the primary production, the farmer who plants, grows, and harvests the crops, who grows/catches fish, or who rears animals for milk or meat. FLW occurring at the primary production stage is commonly referred to as post-harvest loss. Benyam, Soma, and Fraser (2021) state that the factors influencing FLW on farms are

inherently diverse and variable, which makes FLW reduction efforts considerably complex. In addition, they indicate that targeting FLW prevention and reduction is not necessarily considered a priority by framers, although it may indirectly assist in improving their economic returns and contribute to positive environmental outcomes.

Lemaire and Limbourg (2019) observe various causes of FLW at the primary production stage. They mention natural disasters, severe weather conditions, quality standards set by large-scale distributors (weight, size, shape, and appearance), damages during harvesting and market price. Cattaneo et al. (2021) and Delgado, Schuster, and Torero (2021) add to this list: inadequate harvesting time, practices applied at harvest and handling, challenges in marketing produce, and lack of economic incentives to prevent losses. Finally, Despoudi (2021) adds a lack of understanding of the changing market requirements and the changing regulations and a lack of farm-related skills.

In economic terms, when the market price is lower than the harvesting cost, products that are mature for harvest/slaughter/catch, perfectly edible are left on the field. To combat such losses, farmers may produce more than requested and not market the surplus to avoid a price decrease (agreements with retail chains) (Priefer, Jörissen, and Bräutigam 2016). This illustrates how supply chain interactions create unavoidable FLW.

Post-harvest losses can be significant and differ strongly per product category. Arias Bustos and Moors (2018) for example studied food loss and waste in the production of avocados and estimated this to amount to 5-25%. Other sources, such as Lipinski et al. (2016), have found similar percentages of about 40% overall for fruit and vegetables. It can reasonably be expected that absolute food loss will increase with increasing production levels.

3.3 Processing

Food processors are the next actor in an FSC and depending on the product in scope multiple processing stages can follow each other, resulting in primary, secondary, tertiary etc processors. Processed foods are generally thought to be inferior to unprocessed foods. They may bring to mind a packaged food item containing many ingredients, perhaps even artificial colors, flavors, or other chemical additives. Often referred to as convenience or pre-prepared foods, processed foods are suggested to be a contributor to the obesity epidemic and rising prevalence of chronic diseases like heart disease and diabetes¹. According to the FUSIONS project, see Stenmarck et al. (2016), this stage is responsible for the second-largest amount of FLW, only after the consumer stage. However, they also state that the processing industry is perhaps the most difficult stage to measure FLW. Still, these actors are especially important for avoiding food waste. Augustin et al. (2016) describe the role of food processors as “to increase the useful life of foods, optimize nutrient availability and food quality, and reduce losses and waste.” In addition, effective integration of processing companies within the whole food system is important to reduce food waste (Manzini and Accorsi 2013). Figure 8 summarizes the role of processing in the FSC.

¹ <https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/nutritionsource/processed-foods/>

Figure 8. Optimization of value across the FSC, from (Augustin et al. 2016)

Food processing contributes to the reduction of FLW by using preservation processes, such as freezing, drying, fermentation, canning, pasteurization and sterilization, and packaging technologies to increase the shelf-life of products. Waste in food processing has increased because of the shift of the food industry's towards refined single food components (e.g. protein, vitamins), a food product or ingredient with a defined composition (e.g. whey protein concentrate) or a food product that meets standards for appearance (e.g. acceptable coloured and shaped fruits and vegetables) (Augustin et al. 2016). These strict requirements result in an increased flow of by-products that are removed from the end products but are perfectly edible and could be used in other products. For example, by-products of processed apple pomace (the pulpy residue remaining after the apple has been crushed in order to extract its juice) such as dietary fibre (pectin, hemicelluloses, cellulose and lignin) and phenolic compounds (flavonols, phenolic acids, dihydrochalcones and anthocyanins) may be extracted and put back into the food chain (Rabetafika et al. 2014). Furthermore, as observed by Raza et al. (2020), food processors play a critical role in reducing FLW by enhancing the bioavailability of nutrients and improving sensory characteristics and properties of food, as well as by destroying foodborne microbes and toxins and improving food safety.

3.4 Logistics and distribution

The third actor that is commonly identified in an FSC is the food distributor and logistics operators. Unlike is suggested by traditional conceptual frameworks for FLW, logistics and distribution can take place after every other entity that is described in this chapter. Depending on the phase of the food system, this may relate to B2B bulk shipping, transport of semi-processed intermediate products, doorstep delivery to consumers, etc. Relatively little has been published on the role of this entity in (the reduction of) FLW, but their role has become increasingly important. Lemaire and Limbourg (2019) discuss how globalisation, urbanisation, and industrialisation of food production have led to food supply networks that

are increasingly complex, international, and interconnected. This changes the most effective production process and delivery of food. Bloemhof and Soysal (2017) observe that perishable food products travel long distances from production to consumption and yet have competitive prices. This increases the importance of distributors who manage longer so-called cold chains², with more intermediaries, and increased risks of losses (Priefer, Jörissen, and Bräutigam 2016).

Paciarotti and Torregiani (2021) reviewed alternatives for the globalising FSCs, which they collectively defined as short food supply chain (SFSC) initiatives. We observe that SFSCs have recently become more prevalent, but their logistics are still a challenging issue. In their paper, the authors define several interventions to be implemented to effectively improve SFSC, mostly from a supply chain infrastructure and -management point of view. The virtues of SFSCs are confirmed by Do et al. (2021), who mentioned this as a condition for the shift towards a more sustainable production and consumption model. It is important to realize, though, that reducing FLW through SFSCs cannot be achieved by the voluntary action of the logistics industry alone. In fact it may involve rethinking the complete supply chain model (Muriana 2017). SFSC relate directly to the concept of food miles, as discussed by Govindan (2018). Food miles at present cover long distances resulting not only in FLW but also in high transport cost. Due to the globalization of food production, the transport of food has a high impact on the environment.

Several papers have been published investigating the effect of applying different technologies or management strategies in the food supply chain through simulation modelling. For instance, Nikolicic et al. (2021) investigate the effect that changes in inventory management supported by the application of RFID and modern information and communication technologies have on the amount of food waste. The authors conclude that both food waste and stocks in supermarkets and producers are significantly reduced, without having a significant impact on the number of stock-outs, when there is synchronization of information and product flow in the distribution part of the supply chain.

Also, Leithner et al. (2019) investigate the benefits of facilitating real-time product data along delivery and storage processes. The authors indicate that the consideration of shelf-life data in supply chain decisions allows to reduce food losses and further enables shifting surplus inventory to alternative distribution channels.

3.5 Distribution/wholesale

Fresh or processed food products, before going to (smaller) retail or foodservice, in many cases, transit via a wholesale step. We will discuss the role of this FSC stage in FLW in this section. For fresh products, an additional step in the FSC typically goes hand in hand with temperature-controlled conditioning. Jedermann et al. (2014) observe that a considerable share of FLW is caused by non-optimal cold chain processes and management.

Wholesalers also play a role in the packaging and portioning of food. Wohner et al. (2020) present an evaluation method for food-packaging systems. First, they determine food waste due to poor packaging that is difficult for consumers to empty completely. Then, these quantities were included in life cycle assessments (LCA) of the products to identify the most sustainable food packaging system. As a case study, four different ketchup products were

² A cold chain, according to WHO is defined as “An unbroken cold chain is an uninterrupted series of refrigerated production, storage and distribution activities, along with associated equipment and logistics, which maintain quality via a desired low-temperature range.”

examined. For example, for ketchup in polypropylene bottles, FLW resulting from poor emptiability ranged from 13% to 29%, while this was only 4% for ketchup packaged in glass.

Wholesale actors are also of importance since they have a bit more flexibility in the product characteristics they accept. Chaboud and Moustier (2021) found that farmers who sold exclusively to wholesalers (traders) claimed to sell downgraded and/or damaged produce significantly more easily than farmers who only sold to supermarkets. The high-quality standards of retail, foodservice and, in the end, consumers are discussed in the next sections.

3.6 Retail

A relatively small percentage of FLW (together with wholesale about 5%, see Figure 5) occurs at the retail³ stage of the FSC. But still, retail plays a key role in the avoidance of FLW. Obviously, retail has clear incentives to increase operational efficiency and generate turnover out of the ingredients/products they purchased. This part of FLW reduction therefore comes natural to them. But it is less clear what their incentive is to avoid the consumer's food waste, which sometimes entails selling less. This is an important question for the ZEROW project.

In recent years retailers have launched ambitious programs to further reduce FLW in their own operation. Next to FLW generated in the outlets, retailers do have a key role in the FLW reduction via their direct interaction with both the consumers and the producers. By influencing consumer behaviour, the indirect influence of retailers can be significant. For example, Wang, Yuan, and Tang (2021) describe how for FLW generated in the retail stage, the European Commission⁴ approved in 2008 the phasing out of regulations on marketing standards on the size and shapes of fruit and vegetables to prevent fruits and vegetables with slight aesthetic abnormalities from being thrown away.

The motivations of retailers for reducing FW are economic and moral (Lemaire and Limbourg (2019); Gruber, Holweg, and Teller (2016)). Retailers maintain high standards to avoid quality scandals (Priefer, Jörissen, and Bräutigam 2016). And in addition, retailers maintain high levels of inventory to provide choice even to customers that enter the shop just before closing time (Stenmarck et al. 2016). For retailers, in economic terms, availability is often more critical than FLW reduction. According to Lemaire and Limbourg (2019), retailers typically ask suppliers for food products with at least 70% of their shelf lives remaining, which leads to additional FLW at suppliers. Retailers measure the performance of their suppliers in terms of their 'on time in full' performance. Therefore, suppliers prefer waste over stock outs (Mena et al. 2014).

In the EU research project REFRESH Masotti et al. (2019), the authors employ Agent Based Modelling (ABM) as a tool to evaluate food waste reduction innovations among retailers. In particular, they simulate the impact of two innovations: an active packaging, which increases the shelf life of fresh fruit, and a misting technology, used in retailers to increase the shelf life of fresh fruits and vegetables. Their results show that the willingness to innovate among retailers is not only an economic issue, but is influenced by several factors, such as the strong

³ With the term retail, we mean all companies that focus on the sale of goods to the public in relatively small quantities for use or consumption rather than for resale

⁴ Directive (EU) 2018/851 amending directive 2008/98/EC on waste Brussels, Belgium.

connections between retailers or the level of awareness about the existence of innovations to reduce food waste among their customers.

A similar role as the retailers is played by the foodservice sector, which we discuss in the next section.

3.7 Foodservice

Foodservice or the hospitality sector are collective terms for providing meals out of home. Many authors have proposed almost as many categorizations. For example, Katajajuuri et al. (2014) discern the following types:

- Fast-food outlets
- Restaurants, diners, and hotels
- Cafes, petrol stations
- Schools
- Hospitals, elderly service centres
- Workplace and student canteens
- Day-care centres

Perhaps surprisingly, foodservice is responsible for roughly 2.5 times the total FLW generated in the retail and wholesale stages combined, see Figure 5). Filimonau and De Coteau (2019) observe that FLW at foodservice locations has attracted insufficient academic attention to date. In their literature review, they found a relatively small number of academic studies that dealt specifically with hospitality food waste and identified a limited (geographical and operational) scope of analysis. Since food consumption out of home is still growing globally, FLW in the hospitality sector has become increasingly important. Most likely, the 12% of total FLW that is attributed to foodservice by the FUSIONS project (cf Stenmarck et al. (2016)) is an under-estimate; their measurement did not include retail catering, such as coffee shops and supermarket cafes, and contract catering, such as work and hospital canteens.

The drivers for FLW in the foodservice industry are like the ones that apply to the retail sector, but perhaps the quality perceived by consumers is even stronger here than in the retail area. For hotels, Juvan et al. (2021) found that buffets are particularly wasteful. In more detail, they observe that dinner buffets are worse than breakfast buffets; the latest breakfast serving time is worse than the earliest, and high-end breakfast buffets are worse than budget buffets. Finally, the first meal a guest eats at a hotel and the presence of children also lead to more plate waste.

Papargyropoulou et al. (2016) conducted a series of interviews that revealed that restaurants on average prepare 30% more food than what was required by bookings. In addition, quantity choices were based on surpluses served to satisfy the customers' expectations for variety and value for money. Therefore, it is important that lunch buffets did not run out of food, leading to high FLW. Furthermore, portion size is not always aligned with the customer. When the portion size is too big, some restaurants offer the possibility to take the rest of the food back home in a Doggy bag. Sirieix, Lála, and Kocmanová (2017) studied the behavioural reasons for refusing Doggy bags in the Czech Republic. Their results highlight a paradox between norms and emotions: personal norms encourage not to waste while salient social norms encourage leaving leftovers; asking for a doggy bag generates immediate shame while leaving leftovers produces anticipated regret and guilt. Finally, the EU has strict hygiene rules (cf Priefer, Jörissen, and Bräutigam (2016); Lemaire and Limbourg (2019), Martin-Rios

et al. (2018)) as well as strict conservation rules that limit storage and reuse possibilities during cooking.

In line with the above papers, De Waal (2017) notes that the structure of food waste at the household level is based on six phases: planning, purchasing, storing, preparing, consuming and leftover phase. For each of these phases, the autor lists a number of variables that impact on food waste, for instance: degree of inventory checking, degree of overbuying, storage conditions, cooking skills, unpredictable lifestyle, or knowledge of leftovers. Consequently, in order to identify possible interventions, the autor proposes a causal relationship diagram of the total food waste system including the phases and variables listed above. Finally, the author concludes that consumers tend to plan to buy more food than they actually need, store it for extended periods of time and therefore the excess ends up being wasted

3.8 Consumer

By far the largest share of FLW comes from households, about 53%, see Figure 5 based on (Stenmarck et al. 2016). Prices and consumer behaviour are the key factors. Whereas the former is a result of commercial market behaviour, the latter can be influenced by a range of actions such as education, campaigns, popular sources, and cookbooks.

Stefan et al. (2013) find that consumers' planning and shopping routines are important predictors of food waste, and they are determined by moral attitudes towards food waste and sense of control. Therefore, to reduce FLW in the household kitchens, consumers must be provided with skills and tools to deal with their food-related activities. The authors also remark that the acceptance of new food technologies and processing methods is critical for the commercial success of processed foods.

Augustin et al. (2016) mention several different viewpoints concerning consumer food-buying behaviour, ranging from pure utility optimization, need recognition, product marketing, social good, environmental concerns, availability, to health.

Both earned (news) media and social media have a strong influence on consumer buying and cooking behaviour. Conversations on social media can have a strong impact on the food choices and the brands that consumers purchase and thereby be an influencer of healthy choices ((Liu and Lopez 2016)). But still traditional marketing campaigns by food producers and retailers can also have a significant impact on consumer behaviour.

Everyday routines also have an impact. Fanelli (2019) in an online survey in Italy showed that FLW by consumers decreases when individuals buy foods in small markets and with a weekly frequency of two times/week or more. Aureli, Scalvedi, and Rossi (2021) find that foods of high economic value are less wasted compared to foods with low unit cost. Low unit-cost food items are typically purchased in large quantities, leading to an increased FLW. In addition, as observed by Cattaneo et al. (2021), shoppers become less price-sensitive as incomes increase. This is likely to lead to a future increase in food waste in currently low- and middle-income countries.

Papargyropoulou et al. (2016) confirm this by making a case to study food consumption and food waste generation together, rather than separately, to fully understand how, where and food waste is generated. This understanding will then enable research to draw detailed, case-specific food waste prevention plans addressing both the material and socio-economic aspects of food waste generation.

Some other elements that impact FLW levels at consumers are:

- Lack of knowledge (Farr-Wharton, Foth, and Choi (2014); Priefer, Jörissen, and Bräutigam (2016))
- (Geographical) availability (Farr-Wharton, Foth, and Choi 2014)
- Past experience with FLW reduction (Farr-Wharton, Foth, and Choi 2014)
- Attitude-behaviour gap (Schanes, Dobernig, and Gözet 2018)
- Deteriorating cooking skills due to the rise of convenience food (Evans 2011)
- Increasing number of single-person households (Jörissen, Priefer, and Bräutigam 2015)

This short reflection on the role of the consumer in (reducing) FLW concludes our description of the various supply chain actors that must be part of a conceptual model for FLW assessment. In the next section, we will add one more viewpoint, which is not of a specific actor but of the entire society.

4 Food loss and waste – Sources and drivers

In recent years, many literature studies have been performed to identify the sources and drivers behind food waste. In this chapter, we, therefore, do not aim to repeat such a literature study, but we instead summarize the main findings from recent studies. Previous overviews sometimes had a broad scope covering most of the supply chain, but some studies also zoomed in on specific supply chain stages. In general, they discuss their findings across different product categories, not necessarily identifying different drivers behind different products. In this chapter, we structure our discussion around the supply chain stages identified in the previous chapter. For each of these supply chain stages, we provide an overview of the main categories of drivers, including examples of key drivers. The focus will be on identifying what specific drivers play a role in each supply chain stage, while also introducing the more general drivers that lead to waste across the different supply chain stages. These more general drivers do, however, often have specific dynamics in different supply chain stages.

Before discussing the drivers in detail, it is worth noting that many studies have shown that food loss is more prominent early in the supply chain in developing countries and more prominent later in the supply chain in developed countries. To some extent, this will also be clear from the discussion of different drivers, as these are also more or less likely to play a role in developing or developed countries. For instance, many technology-oriented drivers play a stronger role in developing countries (as e.g., refrigerated storage is more likely to be insufficient), and many consumer-behaviour-oriented drivers play a stronger role in developed countries (as e.g., high cosmetic standards are more likely to be demanded).

4.1 Primary production

Table 4 shows an overview of the main driver categories identified for the primary production stage, including an elaboration of the main drivers for each of the categories.

Table 4. Food waste drivers in the primary production stage (based on detailed overviews by Bhattacharya et al. 2021; Dora et al., 2021; Magalhães et al. 2021; Shafiee-Jood and Cai, 2016; Spang et al., 2019).

Driver categories	Key drivers
Environmental conditions	Weather conditions, disease and contaminations, damages by insects/rodents/birds
Standards and regulation	Failure to meet quality standards (weight, shape, size), food safety regulations
Lack of infrastructure or technology	Lack of (adequate) storage facilities, inadequate cultivation or harvesting technology, poor input materials
Lack of skills or expertise	Lack of knowledge on growing techniques and harvest timing, labour shortages
Economic factors and incentives	Crops not harvested due to unfavourable market conditions, overall economic conditions
Supply chain management issues	Inadequate forecasting, overproduction due to uncertain demands or supply agreements, lack of communication and integration

Primary production is the stage in which drivers related to environmental conditions are arguably more relevant than in any other stage. As we see in the table, this is related to, for example, weather conditions, the possibility of disease and contamination, as well as damages by insects or birds.

As in any of the supply chain stages, standards and regulations play a key role. Already this early in the chain, products that do not satisfy often rigorous quality demands will be wasted. Here, quality demands can relate to weight, size, shape, and appearance. This either means that products are left on the field or that they are sorted out soon after they are harvested. Standards and regulations related to food safety might also play a role here, as food can also be wasted due to safety concerns.

The lack of appropriate infrastructure or technology is also mentioned many times in the literature. In primary processing, this mainly relates to technology related to quality preservation (e.g., refrigeration) and harvesting. In addition, the use of lower quality input materials is also mentioned, as this can affect the quantity and quality of the products being produced. It is interesting to note that this would also imply a broader perspective on FLW, as such unrealised yield would typically not be measured. In general, the importance of these drivers related to infrastructure also depends on the context, as these drivers are often much stronger in developing countries.

In addition to technology, the human factor also plays a key role. This for instance concerns the potentially improper handling of delicate products. More specifically, for primary processing, the literature points out the lacking knowledge of cultivation techniques and harvesting timing as important drivers. Like the technological drivers, these expertise-based drivers are often stronger in developing countries.

Economic factors also play a significant role in the primary processing stage. The main issue here is that crops are sometimes left on the field due to unfavourable market conditions: low prices can mean that harvesting efforts are not worth it.

Finally, the literature reports different drivers related to the complexities of supply chain management. Uncertainties related to demand forecasts or harvest yields can lead to overproduction, which in turn leads to products being wasted. This also includes aspects related to how different supply chain actors collaborate and communicate. For instance, to meet supply agreements with retail, overproduction might be unavoidable.

4.2 Distribution/consolidation

After harvesting, during the initial distribution and consolidation of products, many of the food waste drivers present in agriculture still apply, especially since in many cases there is still a lack of adequate infrastructure and technology, and similar environmental conditions influence product degradation. Also, the sorting and possible rejection of products due to quality standards continue during this stage, potentially even more so. Table 5 provides a summary of drivers in this supply chain stage.

Table 5: Food waste drivers in the consolidation and distribution stage (based on detailed overviews by Bhattacharya et al. 2021; Dora et al., 2021; Magalhães et al. 2021; Shafiee-Jood and Cai, 2016; Spang et al., 2019).

Driver categories	Key drivers
Environmental conditions	Weather conditions during drying, microbes and contaminations during storage, damages by insects or rodents
Standards and regulation	Products rejected due to quality standards (weight, shape, size) or food safety concerns
Lack of infrastructure or technology	Lack of (cold) storage or drying facilities, poor road infrastructures and planning equipment, inadequate packaging
Lack of skills or expertise	Improper handling of delicate product, lack of knowledge on waste minimization and reuse, labour shortages
Supply chain management issues	Poor forecasting, overstocking due to uncertain demand and take-back agreements, lack of information sharing, mismanagement of cold chain

During distribution and consolidation, environmental conditions also refer to storage conditions, especially related to products that require drying during this stage. During storage, damages by insects and rodents are also a relevant factor. Especially in developing countries, these environmental conditions play a key role in these early parts of the supply chain.

In terms of skills and expertise, improper handling of delicate products is still a key driver, but during distribution and consolidation, there is also more emphasis on the lack of investment in knowledge regarding postharvest technologies. Furthermore, the improper stacking and overfilling of bins during the distribution process is mentioned as an additional driver.

From a supply chain management perspective, overstocking still plays a significant role, but in this stage, it is not only linked to poor forecasting and uncertainty in demand, but also specifically linked to the existence of take-back agreements. Finally, when cold chains do exist, they are not always managed appropriately, also leading to food waste.

4.3 Processing

A summary of food waste drivers during processing is presented in Table 6. It should be noted that the studies used to create this overview typically do not distinguish between primary or secondary processing, even though some of the mentioned drivers seem more applicable to the primary processing stage in which food products are transformed to commodities (e.g., cutting and trimming losses or processing by-products).

Table 6: Food waste drivers in the processing stage (based on detailed overviews by Bhattacharya et al. 2021; Dora et al., 2021; Magalhães et al. 2021; Raak et al., 2017; Shafiee-Jood and Cai, 2016; Spang et al., 2019).

Driver categories	Key drivers
Processing characteristics	Cutting and trimming losses; product samples for QC/QA or R&D, losses during product changeovers and cleaning, processing by-products
Standards and regulation	Products rejected due to quality standards (including visual characteristics) or food safety concerns
Lack of infrastructure or technology	Lack of (adequate/efficient) processing and storage facilities, poor packaging, equipment defects
Lack of skills or expertise	Improper handling of products, processing inefficiency or defects due to human error or lack of skilled staff
Supply chain management issues	Overstocking due to uncertainty/take-back agreements, lack of attention to by-products, lack of information sharing, inadequate inventory management, interruption of cold chain

High quality standards for products remain a challenge in this stage of the supply chain, but now also extends to processed food products, which often also have strict guidelines on visual characteristics.

Lack of adequate infrastructure and technology concerns processing and packaging aspects here, which includes lacking technology for quality preservation, defective equipment, and inadequate packaging technology. Skills and expertise of operators in processing environments also contribute to drivers: process inefficiencies and defective products can be caused by a lack of skilled staff (or general human error).

In addition to lacking processing technology, several inherent characteristics of processing activities lead to food waste drivers. During processing, parts of the food products used as ingredients might be trimmed, leading to losses. This includes both edible food losses and inedible by-products that might still have other uses. In many processing environments, part of the production volume is furthermore lost due to product sampling for destructive quality-control tests and due to losses around product changeovers and cleaning operations.

Finally, supply chain management aspects also play a key role in driving food waste in the processing stage. In addition to the overstocking due to uncertainty and take-back agreements, the lack of information sharing as well as inadequate inventory management are mentioned as drivers. Also, the lack of attention to by-product flows in supply chain management activities is relevant here as processing activities are a major source of by-products.

4.4 Distribution/wholesale

After processing, in the distribution and wholesale stage, two categories of food waste drivers are most prominent in the literature: drivers related to lacking infrastructure and technology and drivers related to supply chain management. An overview of the key drivers is included in Figure 7.

Table 7: Food waste drivers in the distribution and wholesale stage (based on detailed overviews by Bhattacharya et al. 2021; Dora et al., 2021; Magalhães et al. 2021; Shafiee-Jood and Cai, 2016; Spang et al., 2019; Surucu-Balci and Tune, 2021).

Driver categories	Key drivers
Lack of infrastructure or technology	Lack of (adequate/efficient) logistics infrastructure (i.e., transport, storage, material handling), poor packaging
Lack of skills or expertise	Improper handling of products during transport, storage, packaging
Standards and regulation	Products rejected due to quality standards (including visual characteristics) or food safety concerns
Economic factors and incentives	Inefficient procurement channels, high transportation costs, lack of incentives to reduce waste
Supply chain management issues	Poor forecasting practices, inefficient inventory management, logistics constraints, lack of communication/coordination/collaboration, mismanagement of cold chain, managing promotions and seasonality

In addition to the two mentioned categories, drivers related to quality standards and improper product handling skills also remain part of the discussion in the literature. Product handling issues in this stage specifically relate to moving products in and out of storage and transportation equipment. Also, some economic factors and incentives are mentioned: high transportation costs and a lack of incentives to reduce food waste are part of these discussions.

The lack of infrastructure and technology in this stage is mostly related to inadequate cold chain technology. Proper cold chain logistics equipment for storage and transportation is clearly key and lacking or inadequate transportation equipment or cold storage facilities is a key driver mentioned by many authors. In addition, poor product packaging material is also mentioned within this category.

Since this supply chain stage purely deals with logistics activities, it might not be surprising that there are many food waste drivers related to supply chain management issues mentioned in the literature. Like other supply chain stages, lacking communication and supply chain collaboration are mentioned. More specific logistics-related drivers are found in relation to poor forecasting practices and inefficient inventory management, but the literature also mentions aspects like the proliferation of product portfolios, the management of promotions and seasonality.

Many of the drivers mentioned in this stage are more relevant in developed countries, as the distribution and wholesale stages are often more prominent in the more professionalized, longer supply chains found in those countries.

4.5 Retail

Table 8 contains an overview of the key drivers identified for the retail stage of the supply chain. In general, we continue to see quality standards play a similar role as in other supply chain stages, but we see some retail-specific aspects mentioned in relation to other driver categories. The underlying studies do not specifically exclude certain types of retail but seem to mostly be relying on data from traditional brick-and-mortar retail environments.

Table 8: Food waste drivers in the processing stage (based on detailed overviews by Bhattacharya et al. 2021; de Moraes et al., 2020; Dora et al., 2021; Magalhães et al. 2021; Shafiee-Jood and Cai, 2016; Spang et al., 2019).

Driver categories	Key drivers
Lack of infrastructure or technology	Lack of (adequate/efficient) storage and refrigeration infrastructure (including managing donations), inadequate packaging
Lack of skills or expertise	Improper handling of products, inappropriate work procedures, poor organisation culture regarding waste
Standards and regulation	Products rejected due to quality standards (including visual defects) or food safety concerns
Economic factors and incentives	Inefficient procurement channels, lack of managerial incentives to reduce waste, fear of lawsuits for donation
Supply chain management issues	Poor forecasting practices, inefficient inventory management, logistical inefficiencies, lack of communication/coordination/collaboration, mismanagement of cold chain, managing seasonality
Retail practices	Inefficient in-store management, inflexibility with promotions and presentation, a wide range of products and brands

In relation to infrastructure and technology, lacking or inadequate cold chain equipment, as well as poor packaging, are still prominent food waste drivers mentioned by many authors. The lack of infrastructure, however, also extends to managing waste streams, and some of the literature specifically mentions the lack of access to recycling and collection for composting, as well as the lack of storing and transporting infrastructure for the donation of surplus product to organizations such as food banks.

The lack of a donation infrastructure is also mentioned within food waste drivers related to economic factors and incentives. More specifically, the literature points to the fear of lawsuits in relation to donations: if donated food led to food safety issues after donation, retailers could be held responsible or incur reputational damage. In addition to a general lack of incentives to reduce waste, this even adds an incentive against redistribution. A

similar incentive exists due to a fear of finding donated products back on grey markets, which retailers would also like to prevent,

Food waste drivers in the skills and expertise category relate to improper handling of delicate fresh products. But some of the literature also emphasizes the lack of knowledge on recycling and waste minimization, as well as the presence of a poor organisational culture with regards to waste reduction.

Many supply chain management issues are mentioned as food waste drivers in the retail stage. Inefficiencies in inventory management and resulting expiry date problems are a key driver here. Also connected to poor forecasts and lacking communication and collaboration with other supply chain actors, managing inventories can be difficult.

Finally, the literature also identifies some drivers related to retail practices. Especially in this stage of the supply chain, a wide range of products and brands is often present, complicating the supply chain management issues mentioned above. More specifically, factors such as promotions lead to significant fluctuations in sales volume, and the visual aspects of stores sometimes also lead to overstocking.

4.6 Foodservice

For the foodservice part of the supply chain, the literature also identifies a variety of specific food waste drivers in addition to some of the more general issues present across the supply chain. Table 9 contains an overview of the key drivers in this part of the supply chain.

Table 9: Food waste drivers in the processing stage (based on detailed overviews by Bhattacharya et al. 2021; de Moraes et al., 2020; Dora et al., 2021; Juvan et al., 2021; Magalhães et al. 2021; Spang et al., 2019).

Driver categories	Key drivers
Lack of infrastructure or technology	Lack of (adequate/efficient) storage and refrigeration infrastructure (including for managing donations), inadequate waste management
Lack of skills or expertise	Improper handling of products, lack of meal preparations and planning skills (including minimizing trimmings and use of leftovers), poor organisation culture regarding waste
Standards and regulation	Products rejected due to quality standards (including visual defects) or food safety concerns, sociocultural standards related to e.g., portioning
Economic factors and incentives	Lack of managerial incentives to reduce waste, low price of food encourages over-ordering
Supply chain management issues	Overproduction due to uncertain demand, inefficient inventory management, lack of communication/coordination/collaboration, managing seasonality
Foodservice practices	Standard serving sizes, fear of lawsuits for donation, menu choices, amount of food on display
Consumer behaviour	Lack of food waste awareness, overestimating portion size, attitude towards taking leftovers home

In terms of skills and expertise, food waste drivers in food service also relate to inadequate skills related to planning and preparing meal production. This, for instance, includes lacking skills to manage leftovers, poor cutting and trimming practices, and inadequate judgement of portion sizes. The literature also mentions poor organisation culture regarding waste reduction and a lack of knowledge on reuse and recycling options are drivers in the food service stage.

Several foodservice practices are also linked to food waste drivers. More specifically, choices in relation to the menu, the amount of food on display, as well as serving sizes are all mentioned in the literature as key drivers in this context. Some of the drivers found in the retail stage are also relevant here: overstocking of food for visual purposes as well as pricing strategies and promotional activities leading to fluctuations in supply and demand for certain products.

In the context of foodservice, environments, food waste drivers related to consumer behaviour also play a role. A general lack of food waste awareness among consumers might lead to significant plate waste, especially in environments in which consumers get to serve themselves (e.g., in a buffet setting). Here, overestimating portion sizes plays a role as well as the customer's attitude with regard to taking leftovers home from the foodservice setting.

4.7 Consumer

The consumer stage is known to be a significant source of food waste, especially in developed countries (see Figure 5). Table 10 summarizes the key drivers behind food waste in this final stage of the supply chain.

Table 10: Food waste drivers in the processing stage (based on detailed overviews by Bhattacharya et al. 2021; de Moraes et al., 2020; Dora et al., 2021; Magalhães et al. 2021; Shafiee-Jood and Cai, 2016; Spang et al., 2019).

Driver categories	Key drivers
Lack of infrastructure or technology	Lack of (appropriate) storage and refrigeration at households, lack of access to waste management services (e.g., recycling, composting)
Lack of skills or expertise	Improper handling of products, lack of knowledge on using leftovers, lacking awareness regarding food waste, lack of understanding of labelling, lack of expertise in assessing food safety
Standards and regulation	Products rejected due to quality standards (including visual defects) or food safety concerns, social norms
Purchasing behaviour	Overbuying discounted products, lack of inventory management skills, packaging sizes too large
Socio-cultural aspects	Experience with food, perceived value of food, norms and attitudes towards food waste, social norms around eating

As in previous supply chain stages, some lack of infrastructure or technology is mentioned here as a driver as well. More specifically, inadequate storage and refrigeration can be a driver, as well as a lack of access to recycling or composting options.

In the category related to lacking skills and expertise, the literature identifies several specific drivers. In addition to more general product handling skills, there is specific mention of lacking skills in relation to food safety assessment, understanding product (date) labels, food preparation, and how to use leftovers. Also, the lack of awareness regarding food waste is also mentioned as a driver in this category.

The purchasing behaviour of customers also relates to a series of food waste drivers. Difficulties with inventory management can be a key driver, partly related to the management of uncertainties in demand and current inventory (e.g., not using a shopping list), but also due to the sizing of packages, and overbuying behaviour caused by discounted products. This waste driver connects to retailer practices, and misalignment of incentives, as additional sales are clearly beneficial for retailers, and not whether consumers reduce waste.

Many socio-cultural aspects further add food waste drivers. A lower perceived value of food is, for instance, mentioned in the literature, as well as the experience with specific food products, attitudes towards food waste, social norms around eating, and individual eating habits.

Especially in the consumer stage, many behavioural and socio-cultural factors lead to food waste drivers and the overview included here only provides a brief overview of the main categories. As mentioned in the introduction of this chapter, this report only aims to provide a general overview of the main categories of drivers for each stage. For a more detailed discussion of individual drivers, we refer to the references used in this chapter.

5 Food loss and waste – Reduce and reuse interventions

In this chapter, we discuss some prominent existing interventions to reduce FLW and therefore present all nine SILLs of the ZEROW project.

5.1 Existing FLW reduction Interventions

Jedermann et al. (2014) investigate FLW prevention intervention through the lenses of digital tools, models, and applications that monitor the changes in food product shelf-life. The paper mentions three case studies on cold supply chains (also called cold chains) and a post-harvest treatment where such intervention is performed through better supervision on food quality maintenance and a better shelf-life prediction model using advanced sensing and digital technologies. A key finding reported in this paper is that vertical information exchange among the retailers and suppliers can lead to more accurate and timely demand forecasting, thereby considerably reducing FLW. Thus, a lot of emphasis is placed on exploiting the food product's shelf-life information for supply chain planning phase. This has a direct impact on food warehouse management and FLW occurring at the warehouse.

Lipinski et al. (2016) report several analyses of global FLW performed with data from 2009. They put forward several recommendations for FLW reduction interventions, which are confirmed by a recent review paper by Moraes, Lermen, and Echeveste (2021):

- **Developing a uniform protocol for FLW measurement** – FAO and EU are developing such standardised protocols for FLW monitoring focusing on developing nations and European member states, respectively. In addition to that, WRAP, UNEP, and FAO are working together to implement an FLW measurement system for corporate supply chains. Data gathered by such regional, national, European wide efforts will lead to accurate, timely interventions by stakeholders.
- **Setting FLW reduction targets** – The EU has already set an ambitious target to halve the FLW by 2030 and achieve nearly zero FLW by 2050 (see Section **Error! Reference source not found.**). This target will be broken down into quantifiable, time-bound national, regional, and corporate FLW prevention targets. They must be monitored through periodic assessments such that global target tracking and progress towards those targets remain in focus.
- **Increase investment in reducing post-harvest losses** – the authors have argued that the post-harvest loss interventions should be translated to specific socio-economic, business, and political contexts. Suggested strategies include building advanced awareness across the entire value chain, equipping them with technically and financially sustainable tools and techniques, capacity building, establishing region specific post-harvest working groups, among others.
- **Creating organisations devoted to reducing FLW** – setting up and supporting private, non-profit (e.g., WRAP UK), or other types of organisations are necessary that will devote their efforts to prevent and reduce FLW. Sustainable financing through a combination of public funding, philanthropy, service-based fee is necessary for them to accelerate and support collaborative initiatives for preventing FLW.

Caldeira, De Laurentiis, and Sala (2019) assessed 91 food waste prevention actions from food value chain actors and classified them into five high-level interventions:

1. Redistribution of surplus food for human consumption
2. Food valorisation where food items are converted into other value-added products (e.g., animal feed, compost)

3. Active promotion of behavioural change among consumers (e.g., developing digital tools guiding consumer towards reduction of FLW, awareness creation on harmful effects of FLW to the environment)
4. Supply chain efficiency improvement (e.g., novel packaging improving product shelf life, thereby decreasing FLW)
5. FLW prevention governance

The report considered six criteria for evaluating an intervening action on food waste prevention – (a) quality of the action design, (b) effectiveness, (c) efficiency, (d) sustainability of the action over time, (e) transferability and scalability, and (f) inter-sectorial cooperation. Each of the above criteria is further subcategorised for deeper evaluation. For example, efficiency is measured against five dimensions – amount of FLW prevented, net economic benefit, net environmental savings, social benefits, and outreach/awareness/behavioural change triggered.

The research presented in (Aramyan et al. 2021) categorises food waste reduction interventions into technological, organisational, and marketing innovations. It is reported that there are several factors that prevent innovative technological innovations from being adopted at scale in the agri-food value chain for FLW reduction intervention. Such factors include – (a) limited economic incentives and high risks (e.g., low Return on Investment, low margin operation resulting in long time for Return on Investment, innovations not being very cost-effective), (b) non-acceptance of consumers (e.g., fresh milk carton is often preferred over high shelf-life milk carton), and (c) territorial specificities arising from social and cultural barriers. In terms of adopting state-of-the-art technological innovations, the report has classified the EU member states into innovators (Sweden, Denmark), early adopters (Italy, France, and The Netherlands), and laggards (Eastern European countries). On the other hand, interventions related to organisational innovation combines information and communication technologies (ICT) with new business models. Hospitality organisations have used and promoted mobile and web apps to alleviate food waste issue. Such apps connect surplus and close to expiry food directly to consumers and include Food for all in Boston and New York, Nofoodwasted in The Netherlands, goMkt in New York City, TooGoodToGo in Western Europe. Marketing innovation-based interventions are developed after through market analyses, research on market segmentation, price-setting strategy, promotion (e.g., “buy one, get one later” used by Sainsbury and Tesco in the UK instead of “buy one get one free”), and more. Interaction among the three types of innovations can lead to the best possible food waste reduction interventions, as highlighted by Aramyan et al. (2021).

Wang, Yuan, and Tang (2021) also summarised possible FLW reduction techniques applicable to the FSC, and categorized them into reduction strategies in developed countries, in developing countries, and strategies aimed at reduced barrier and strengthening enablers. In addition to that, the authors discuss FLW recycling through converting them into animal feed, anaerobic digestion, and composting as well as FLW disposal.

Diaz-Ruiz et al. (2019) evaluated 48 measures, seven of which were labelled ‘highly effective’:

- Education in values and valuing food and diet
- Awareness campaigns to increase consumer concern
- Change of habits to reduce food waste volumes
- School teaching on food waste
- Promoting food purchase planning
- Promoting a strategic food access plan
- Network to redistribute and use farm surpluses

The full list of potential measures that the authors proposed in their survey can be found in Annex 3. In the next subsection, we turn to the specific interventions (SILLs) that will be assessed in the ZEROW project.

5.2 Interventions studied in ZEROW SILLs

In their literature review, Wang, Yuan, and Tang (2021) find that although growing efforts have been made to change consumers' behaviour, most research focuses on analysing the current situation rather than solutions. They encourage experiments or interventions to provide more effective solutions. That is why the ZEROW project has a largely experimental approach that is focused on scalable applications.

This report is part of work package 1 of the ZEROW project, which has as one of its goals to assess the FLW reduction potential of the nine SILLs that are part of the project. In other words, how much food loss or waste can be avoided if these innovations were scaled up to a pan-European level. To answer this scaling question, which was also highlighted by Delgado, Schuster, and Torero (2021), we need to make sure that the conceptual model that underlies the economic model of work package 1 is able to capture the results of the efforts made in each of the nine SILLs. To achieve this goal, we interviewed the leaders of each SILL individually in February 2022. We used a structured interview protocol for this, which is provided in Annex 1: SILL interview protocol.

In the next subsections, we will provide the information and insights gathered during the interviews. Every SILL, after an illustration coming from their initial SILL presentation, will be summarized in a standardized table, and based on that, we will formulate the specific requirements or wishes that a SILL brings for the to be developed conceptual model and consecutive macro-economic model. These possible extensions are summarized in Section 6 and serve as a lengthy list of input for the final conceptual model.

5.2.1 SILL 1: FLW monitoring & assessment

Figure 9 SILL 1: FLW monitoring and assessment (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 5. SILL 1 summary

1	<p>Objective</p> <p>(i) To deliver and pilot an open IT-based solution for capturing FLW data throughout the supply chain and providing analytics to address the requirements of the SDG Indicator 12.3.1 (Global Food Loss and Waste), the Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597 and the Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/2000; (ii) To demonstrate the FLW monitoring & assessment solution in two EU countries, including Estonia, to ensure its applicability and replicability in different business and cultural settings.</p>
2	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Improve business performance of food chain actors</p> <p>Improve sustainability</p>
3	<p>Food Loss or Waste focus</p> <p>Both</p>

- 4 **Change of definition needed**
Maybe
 - 5 **Most relevant FLW destinations**
The primary purpose of our SILL is to monitor and assess the data of FLW in the supply chain, analyse it, and only then try to reduce it. Nevertheless, goal is to get FLW as much high in FLW hierarchy as possible.
 - 6 **Which parts of the Food chain**
All
 - 7 **Food material type**
Both food and associated inedible parts
 - 8 **Food category**
Fruits; Vegetables
 - 9 **Geography**
Regional (Pomurje region in Slovenia). But FLW platform methodology could be with adjustment used in the other areas, countries, etc.
 - 10 **Data availability a challenge?**
Average. Data are the backbone of our SILL. We are now studying and assessing different data sources, their availability, and their collection possibilities.
 - 11 **How to measure success**
The end product is the FLW platform (leading indicator). Other indicators are model or basic FLW platform (M14), the test version of the FLW platform (testing and validated in our Living lab) (M36), and the month M46 definitive version of the FLW platform. It will be further developed in our strategic plan.
 - 12 **Expected time frame for results**
3-4 years
-

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

Most models and definitions of FLW start from the moment of harvesting or later. This SILL, however, explicitly covers the whole FSC from pre-harvest to consumption. This encompasses FLW even at the pre-harvest phase. It is therefore important in our extended conceptual model to include pre-harvest. Indeed, based on the interviews with project- and SILL stakeholders, it turns out that a significant share of produced plants and crops are for several reasons not harvested. This is an important aspect that should not be overlooked and will therefore be included in our conceptual model, acknowledging that this is a difficult topic due to the lack of data and measuring methods.

Another goal of SILL 1 is to discriminate between distinct types of (secondary) use of FLW. By having a clear view on how and where FLW manifests itself, it becomes possible to strategically (re-)use it for other purposes. In other words, knowing more about the potential use of FLW make reduction targets much more actionable. In addition, it helps to get FLW as high in the repurposing hierarchy as possible. This means that our conceptual model should be able to make a distinction between diverse types of FLW instead of a single comprehensive quantity.

Next, the geographical focus of this SILL will grow during the project. The initiative will start in Slovenia, but the goal is to make the data platform replicable to all other European countries, so that the initiative can be scaled in the coming years. It is therefore important to consider adding a geographical scope element to the conceptual model.

Finally, SILL 1 chooses to focus on the food categories of fruit and vegetables. This means that other categories such as grains, protein foods, or dairy are not in scope. Therefore, this could also be a new requirement for our conceptual model.

5.2.2 SILL 2: Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh food

Figure 10. Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh Food products (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 6. SILL 2 summary

1	<p>Objective</p> <p>(1) to demonstrate the use of a combined intelligent-functional-sustainable packaging solution, combining biobased & biodegradable materials, packaging design and freshness indicators (intelligent label) to significantly reduce food waste and unsustainable packaging at the retail and consumer levels; (2) to demonstrate the use of software for reading freshness colour changes of the intelligent packaging and transforming them into remaining shelf life, to allow retailers better manage their stock and reduce food waste.</p>
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- 2 **Motivation**
 - Improve food security
 - Improve business performance
 - Improve sustainability
 - 3 **Food Loss or Waste focus**
 - Both
 - 4 **Change of definition needed**
 - No
 - 5 **Most relevant FLW destinations**
 - Bio-based materials/biochemical processing
 - Landfill
 - Refuse/discards/litter
 - Foodbanks or similar
 - 6 **Which parts of the Food chain**
 - Post-harvest production
 - Storage
 - Transport
 - Packaging
 - Retail
 - Food service
 - 7 **Food material type**
 - Both food and associated inedible parts
 - 8 **Food category**
 - Protein foods (oily fish)
 - 9 **Geography**
 - Spain, later to be rolled-out to other countries
 - 10 **Data availability a challenge?**
 - A bit, but most needed data are generated within the own SILL
 - 11 **How to measure success**
 - Qualitative based on colour changes of freshness indicator which is related to shelf-life and product conservation.
-

12 **Expected time frame for results**

3-4 years

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

When moving through the FSC from production to consumption, food is lost or wasted with a certain probability. This probability is highly context-specific, but this SILL proposes several interventions that can be used to reduce this probability of food getting lost or wasted. This happens at the production stage (improved tray lids) and at the consumption stage (improved and dynamic best before dates).

5.2.3 SILL 3: wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre)harvesting aligned with short-term demand

Figure 11. SILL3: wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre)harvesting aligned with short-term demand (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 7. SILL 3 summary

1 **Objective**

To demonstrate innovations for food loss reduction at the pre-harvest and harvest stages of fruit & vegetable greenhouse farms through: (i) novel remote sensing solutions enabling accurate crop monitoring, fruit ripeness and yield estimation; (ii) automated produce quality evaluation and estimation of 'sub-standard' produce at the pre-harvest and harvest stages; (iii) data-driven optimisation of combined harvest scheduling and short-term predicted downstream demand.

- 2 **Motivation**
Improve business performance
Improve sustainability
 - 3 **Food Loss or Waste focus**
Food loss
 - 4 **Change of definition needed**
No
 - 5 **Most relevant FLW destinations**
Animal Feed
Landfill
Not harvested/plowed in
 - 6 **Which parts of the Food chain**
Pre-harvest production
Harvest
Wholesalers
 - 7 **Food material type**
Food only
 - 8 **Food category**
Fruits
Vegetables
 - 9 **Geography**
Lithuania, later to be extended
 - 10 **Data availability a challenge?**
A bit.
 - 11 **How to measure success**
By measuring the increase in production and, thus, the reduction of FLW. And by measuring the decrease of operational cost.
 - 12 **Expected time frame for results**
1-2 years.
-

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

This SILL focusses specifically on the operation and yield-maximization of greenhouses. Since this controlled environment is a quite different context compared to open-air food production, it is worthwhile to consider separate production entities for this in the conceptual framework of the FSC.

5.2.4 SILL 4: Mobile Food valorisation as a service

Figure 12. SILL 4: Mobile Food valorisation as a Service (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 8. SILL 4 summary

1	<p>Objective</p> <p>(i) to demonstrate innovative, flexible, and versatile solutions as a service for optimising the use of edible biomass (fresh produce and edible fractions); (2) to demonstrate the economic viability of the business model applied and how the revenues will be distributed throughout the new value chains.</p>
2	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Improve food security</p> <p>Improve business performance</p> <p>Improve sustainability</p>
3	<p>Food Loss or Waste focus</p> <p>Both</p>
4	<p>Change of definition needed</p> <p>No</p>

5 **Most relevant FLW destinations**

Animal feed
Land application
Foodbanks or similar

6 **Which parts of the Food chain**

Post-harvest production

7 **Food material type**

Food only

8 **Food category**

Fruits
Vegetables

9 **Geography**

Flanders

10 **Data availability a challenge?**

Average

11 **How to measure success**

Not clear yet.

12 **Expected time frame for results**

6 months - 2 years

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

This SILL aims at increasing the shelf life of fruits, and at reducing harvest losses. In that way the possibilities for reaching a consumer are increased. It is, however, observed that in the current situation, prices are too low to harvest class-B fruits (example of berries is used). As a result, they are not picked at all, and therefore lost. Therefore, it can be considered to include pricing and price interventions in the conceptual model.

Furthermore, auctions play a key role in the fruit supply chains and could therefore be modelled as a separate entity.

5.2.5 SILL 5: Ugly Food identification, shelf-life assessment & alternative valorisation

Figure 13. Ugly Food identification, shelf-life assessment & alternative valorisation (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 9. SILL 5 summary

1	<p>Objective</p> <p>(i) to assess the shelf-life and compliance of products to retail requirements (e.g. shape, size, ripeness, defects) at an early stage, by non-destructive analysis and multi-attribute classification techniques, applied to a single fruit/vegetable or to a whole lot/batch; (ii) to use the shelf-life and compliance assessment to reduce FLW at the producer and the retailer side; (iii) to ensure quality products with a known shelf-life at the retailer side, providing market strategies for ugly food and optimise logistics/storage management.</p>
2	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Improve sustainability (shelf-life improvement)</p>
3	<p>Food Loss or Waste focus</p> <p>Food loss</p>
4	<p>Change of definition needed</p> <p>No</p>
5	<p>Most relevant FLW destinations</p> <p>Bio-based materials/biochemical processing</p>

- 6 **Which parts of the Food chain**
 - Harvest
 - Post-harvest production
 - Packaging
 - Retail
 - 7 **Food material type**
 - Food only
 - 8 **Food category**
 - Fruits
 - Vegetables
 - 9 **Geography**
 - Regional: Andalusia
 - 10 **Data availability a challenge?**
 - Average
 - 11 **How to measure success**
 - By the number of companies showing interest in the developed technology.
 - 12 **Expected time frame for results**
 - 1-4 years
-

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

Similarly, to SILL 5, this SILL focusses on valorising certain types of food that do not answer to the high-quality standards of the retail customers, in this case oddly shaped tomatoes. By opening multiple value chains depending on product quality, food loss can be significantly reduced. In the case of tomatoes, the peculiar one can be redirected to a soup-producing facility for example.

In addition, this SILL proposed a way to improve the shelf life of fresh food products. Its innovation is not limited to a single stage of the FSC, but instead can be applied at various stages.

5.2.6 SILL 6: reduction through advanced data-drive production process control and optimization

Figure 14. FLW reduction through advanced data-drive production process control and optimization (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 10. SILL 6 summary

1	<p>Objective</p> <p>(i) to significantly reduce food loss in breaded poultry production (most complex line in the factory, with reference products, cordon bleu, 'Flamenquin') through continuous advanced control & optimisation of the key variables and impacting processes involved, for intermediates and the final product; (ii) to migrate from a human-based, low-automation and reactive, to a data-driven, fully controlled, proactive and optimised system; (iii) to integrate the developed solution in the current Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system of ALDELIS avoiding information silos.</p>
2	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Improve business performance</p> <p>Improve sustainability</p>
3	<p>Food Loss or Waste focus</p> <p>Food loss</p>
4	<p>Change of definition needed</p> <p>No</p>

- 5 **Most relevant FLW destinations**
Refuse/discards/litter
 - 6 **Which parts of the Food chain**
Agriculture processing
Packaging
 - 7 **Food material type**
Food only
 - 8 **Food category**
Protein foods (processed poultry)
 - 9 **Geography**
Local
 - 10 **Data availability a challenge?**
A bit.
 - 11 **How to measure success**
Reduced FLW at processing facility, improved food safety, improved predictability of production and resilience of processing facility.
 - 12 **Expected time frame for results**
3-4 years
-

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

This SILL focuses on reapplying food loss in the production phase as input to the production process of other food items. In that way food loss is largely avoided. This suggests a loop in the conceptual model at the processing stage.

Furthermore, this SILL raises the question of the scope of interventions. Whereas some other SILLs have extensive scaling opportunities, this SILL is more bounded to an individual production facility, and therefore serves as an inspirational example, rather than as a scalable solution.

5.2.7 SILL 7: FLW reduction through efficient Food bank networks

Figure 15. FLW reduction through efficient Food bank networks (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 11. SILL 7 summary

1	<p>Objective</p> <p>(i) to demonstrate innovative solutions that strengthen the role of foodbanks as food waste reduction players; (ii) to help European food banks to professionalise their operations, and as such to reduce food losses throughout the food chains, while at the same time helping more people that are hungry in Europe; (iii) to make foodbank-centred food chains not only more efficient, but at the same time also more just; (iv) to ensure that the conflicts between FLW reduction & food poverty, are adequately addressed</p>
2	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Improve food security</p> <p>Improve business performance</p> <p>Improve sustainability</p>
3	<p>Food Loss or Waste focus</p> <p>Both</p>
4	<p>Change of definition needed</p> <p>Maybe. If donations through food banks would be the result of gleaning activities, this would currently not count as a reduction in food losses, as products left on the field are typically excluded from definitions of FLW. Otherwise, most sources of donation would help reduce FLW, as food is still used for human consumption if it is donated to food banks.</p>
5	<p>Most relevant FLW destinations</p> <p>Foodbanks or similar</p>

6 **Which parts of the Food chain**

Pre-harvest production
Harvest
Post-harvest production
Storage
Transport
Agriculture processing
Packaging
Wholesalers
Retail
Food service
Households

7 **Food material type**

Food only

8 **Food category**

Fruits
Vegetables
Grains
Protein Foods
Dairy

9 **Geography**

local-regional-national scales.

10 **Data availability a challenge?**

Big issue. Compared to typical supply chains, food bank supply chains are relatively informal, low-tech supply chains building on volunteer labour, in which many operations are not documented.

11 **How to measure success**

FLW reduction through redistribution for human consumption, including measures on increased redistribution volumes, but possibly also waste reduction at food banks themselves (after donation). Details still to be discussed with SILL partners.

12 **Expected time frame for results**

1+ years

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

Donations to food banks could come from various supply chain actors, providing opportunities to reduce both food losses and food waste. However, following the current definition of FLW, it is unclear if consumption of food by a food bank client instead of a commercial customer is included in waste levels or not. This is an important change to be made in the definition of FLW, at least for the context of this SILL or project.

5.2.8 SILL 8: Retail Food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications

GC-400

Daily Capacity	400kg/day (2 x 200 kgs)
Function	Drying/Reducing/Deodorizing/Sterilizing
Reduction (Weight & volume)	85%–95%
Dimension	2,400mm x 1,500mm x 1,763mm
Weight	2,500kg

The specifications could be changed for improvement of machine without prior notice.

Figure 16. SILL 8: Retail Food waste valorisation through algae production for high-value applications (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 12. SILL 8 summary

1	<p>Objective</p> <p>(i) to develop an optimal and feasible solution for in-store and in-warehouse FLW pre-treatment (especially fruits & vegetables & animal proteins), addressing waste from stores (and equivalent premises); (ii) to characterise the pre-treated FLW and valorise it into the production of micro-algae; (iii) to develop a reverse logistics processes that take into account safety regulations, business constraints, the complexity of FLW being decentralized in the retail context, and the use of an innovative hermetic container for transportation.</p>
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- 2 **Motivation**
 - Improve business performance
 - Improve sustainability
 - 3 **Food Loss or Waste focus**
 - Food waste
 - 4 **Change of definition needed**
 - No/Maybe
 - 5 **Most relevant FLW destinations**
 - Microalgae feed
 - 6 **Which parts of the Food chain**
 - Wholesalers
 - Retail
 - Foodservice
 - Households
 - Return flows
 - 7 **Food material type**
 - Food only
 - 8 **Food category**
 - To be determined, but presumably a mix of all kinds of food categories
 - 9 **Geography**
 - Portugal
 - 10 **Data availability a challenge?**
 - A bit
 - 11 **How to measure success**
 - GOAL: reduce food waste, namely of fresh food, by finding alternative ways to valorise waste - SUCCESS: ability to evaluate one alternative way to valorise waste (feeding microalgae)
 - GOAL: expand the recyclability of food residues - SUCCESS: ability to successfully develop and evaluate a container to store food residues
 - GOAL: reduce carbon emissions deriving from food waste (and related indicators) - SUCCESS: reduce X% of emissions per TON of waste through news ways of valorisation
-

GOAL: evaluate a new way to valorise food residues through the feeding of microalgae - SUCCESS: ability to successfully demonstrate the biological viability to feed microalgae with food residues mixtures

12 **Expected time frame for results**

1-2 years

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

The innovative processing machine developed and evaluated in this SILL can potentially be applied in multiple stages of the supply chain. In addition, like in SILL 7, the definition of FLW might have to be changed to appreciate the valorisation of food that would otherwise have been discarded.

5.2.9 SILL 9: Fork to Farm to Fork: informing and nudging consumers to make better dietary choices

Figure 17. Fork to Farm to Fork: informing and nudging consumers to make better dietary choices (source: provided by SILL lead)

Table 13. SILL 9 summary

1	<p>Objective</p> <p>(i) to develop recipes with low FLW, high nutritional score, and low environmental impact; (ii) to develop a food label and scores for FLW, nutritional value, and environmental impact, to trigger consumer behavioural change; (iii) to demonstrate the use of macro-scale optimisation models that balance FLW reduction with high nutritional value and food affordability.</p>
2	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Improve sustainability</p>
3	<p>Food Loss or Waste focus</p> <p>Both. Through creating food labels per product, we hope to create behavioural change throughout the entire supply chain (from supplier to consumer).</p>
4	<p>Change of definition needed</p> <p>Yes: A definition across the entire supply chain, instead of only a definition for parts of the supply chain.</p>
5	<p>Most relevant FLW destinations</p> <p>All types.</p>
6	<p>Which parts of the Food chain</p> <p>Focus on households.</p>
7	<p>Food material type</p> <p>Both food and associated inedible parts</p>
8	<p>Food category</p> <p>All</p>
9	<p>Geography</p> <p>First focus on the Netherlands, but application is not bounded to any geography.</p>
10	<p>Data availability a challenge?</p> <p>Average: Data about food loss/waste across the entire supply chain is needed. Furthermore, data about palatability to create recipes is required.</p>
11	<p>How to measure success</p> <p>In case we managed to create an app containing food labels able to create recipes.</p>
12	<p>Expected time frame for results</p> <p>3-4 years</p>

Additional implications of this SILL for the conceptual model

This SILL is the only SILL that is demand driven. All other SILLs develop solutions that improve part of the downstream FSC. The framework should somehow include this consumer-demand-driven focus of SILL 9.

This completes the discussion of the interventions proposed by the nine SILLs conducted as part of the ZEROW project. In the next chapter, we will propose several enrichments of the basic version of the conceptual model introduced earlier in this document, see Figure 4.

6 Food Loss and Waste Conceptual model

In this chapter, we summarize the insights from the literature and from the survey of the ZEROW SILLs to propose several possible extensions to the conceptual framework for modelling FLW as presented in Figure 4. Since the project is currently (June 2022) still in its early phases, it will still have to become clear which of the identified extensions are both possible to include in the macro-economic model under D1.2 and D1.3. Based on the developments in individual SILLs it will also become clear which extensions are necessary for assessing impact and scale-up potential, and which extensions are not.

Table 14. Possible extensions to the FLW conceptual model

Possible framework extension	Motivation
Separate pre-harvest and post-harvest processes	SILL 1
Express FLW in other units than volume (CO ₂ emission, nutrients, euro, natural resources, etc.)	SILL 1
Include food banks	SILL 7
Identify several types of FLW (hierarchy)	SILL 1
Geographical range/scope	SILLs 1, 2
Product categories in scope	SILL 1
Include demand considerations such as food security, dietary preferences, etc	SILLs 7, 9
Probability of turning into food waste, per stage/actor of the FSC	SILLs 2, 4
Discriminate between greenhouses and open-air production location	SILL 3
(Pricing) interventions, to avoid FLW due to economic reasons/frictions	SILLs 4, 5
Consider auctions as a separate supply chain actor	SILL 4
Innovations that are not linked to a single to 1 stage of the supply chain, but can be applied to multiple levels	SILLs 5, 8
Include food redistribution	SILL 7,8
Demand driven vs supply driven FSCs	SILL 9

These possible extensions to the as-is conceptual model, as sketched in Figure 4 are displayed in Figure 18, leading to an enriched conceptual framework for FLW. Considering that we are still in the early phases of the ZEROW project, and both the SILLs and the macro-economic model WP1, still largely must take shape, the list of extensions should be considered as a list of potential extensions that we can foresee at this stage. Which ones will be included in the macro-economic model depends on how work packages 1 and 4 will develop during the project.

Another remark is that every SILL builds on quite specific contexts and assumptions, which ideally results in customized tweaks of the conceptual model. However, the rationale for the conceptual model is that it should be able to model the impact of the interventions of all SILLs to an acceptable level. This calls for a generalizable model based on the largest common denominator over all SILLs.

Figure 18. Enriched conceptual framework for FLW

7 Conclusions and recommendations

As mentioned in the previous chapter, it is still too early for final conclusions regarding the conceptual model for FLW for ZEROW. Instead, in this report, we reviewed, as a first key step, the (academic) literature and surveyed the SILLs to lay a solid foundation for the economic model that will be built in WP1. This model will assess the actual impact of the SILLs and to estimate the potential impact when the SILL interventions are scaled up across the whole European Union.

In this chapter, we will formulate some intermediate conclusions and recommendations based on the early learnings in the ZEROW project and based on literature. Surprisingly, much research has already been done about conceptual models for FLW impact assessment and reduction. A useful review paper is provided by Chauhan et al. (2021). Despite the many research on the topic of FLW, they identify 30 research gaps that are categorized under the following denominators:

- Factors responsible for FLW generation
- Solutions to eliminate FLW
- Impact of FLW reduction
- Sustainability studies
- FLW quantification
- Internet of things (IoT) and use of digital technologies
- Trade-offs

In this concluding chapter, we will as much as possible finetune our conclusions to the specifics of the ZEROW project. In the next three subsections we take the perspectives of the ZEROW consortium, practitioners, and policy makers.

7.1 For the ZEROW consortium

The ZEROW project strongly supports the Sustainable Development Goals, and its intention is to contribute to them reducing FLW. According to Augustin et al. (2016), about 795 million people in the world were undernourished in 2014 while more than 2 billion people were overweight or obese in 2013 (Ng et al. 2014). To be able to feed the world population, which is expected to increase from 7.3 billion today to 9 billion in 2050, an increase in agricultural productivity by 30-40% is required by 2050 just to meet current dietary energy needs. At the highest abstraction level, this energy gap can be closed in three ways according to Keating et al. (2014):

- Reducing demand
- Lessening the current level of food waste
- Increasing food production

Today, FLW statistics are almost entirely based on weight. If we reformulate food demand in terms of calories to fulfil energy needs, fundamental requirements of macronutrients and micronutrients for good health need to be met. Therefore, for example through SILL 9, it is essential to take potential overconsumption of nutrients, changing demographic structure, consumer choices and cultural context of diets into account.

The ZEROW project has a strong focus on perishable crops, as FLW reduction is most challenging for this category, while at the same time, they typically provide valuable nutrients. According to Fabi et al. (2021), losses for perishable crops, such as fruits and vegetables, are roughly twice as high as losses for other crops. In addition, losses are relatively higher in low- and middle-income regions. The latter is important to realize. When in the light of the sustainable development goals, we wish to take a broad perspective, we cannot simply extrapolate the findings for the countries in the European Union. In fact, the situation will be even more challenging in low- and middle-income countries.

A final recommendation for the ZEROW consortium is to always keep the perspective of the overall food system (or Food Supply Chain) into account, although SILLs seemingly focus on a limited part of the FSC. As identified by Katajajuuri et al. (2014), sustainable FLW reduction solutions require close co-operation within the whole supply chain, with government interventions and support. Furthermore, identifying the best practices and effective ways to implement them requires more multidisciplinary research. Food insecurity and sustainability in general, and FLW in particular, are wicked problems that cannot be solved in isolation.

7.2 For practitioners

For the recommendations for practitioners, careful research has already been done by the European Commission, which has resulted in a longlist per FSC stage. Therefore, we suffice here by providing the main recommendation for practitioners as defined by the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste, see Table 15.

Table 15. Recommendations for Action in Food Waste Prevention Developed by the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste⁵

System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop national strategies for preventing and reducing food loss and waste, in line with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Target 12.3. • Integrate food loss and waste reduction as part of food policy strategies and programmes • Integrate food loss and waste reduction as part of climate action strategies and programmes • Scale up food loss and waste prevention action in the food supply chain • Address and fill the data gaps: improve availability and quality of data on food loss and waste levels and their related impacts (social, economic, environmental) • Improve action design, monitoring, evaluation, and knowledge sharing regarding food waste prevention interventions • Integrate food loss and waste in education and professional training, both in public and private sectors
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⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food-waste/eu-actions-against-food-waste/eu-platform-food-losses-and-food-waste_en

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of food waste prevention for all of us in our role as consumers, promoting value of food and working to shift social norms so that wasting food is no longer socially acceptable • Provide information on involvement in food waste prevention actions • Improve use of date marking • Strengthen capacity for innovation, promoting circularity and new market opportunities • Incentivise food waste prevention • Ensure financial (and other) support to help players act in their operations (focus on SMEs, farmers)
<p>Primary production</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct further research on marketing standards • Strengthen the position of food producers in the food supply chain • Better align supply with demand • Improve resource efficiency and reduce food losses in agriculture by improving animal health and welfare and access to innovation • Strengthen financial support to farms to drive modernisation with a focus on tackling food losses and food waste • Include farmers and their cooperatives and farming service providers in research and innovation activities from the beginning of the process
<p>Manufacturing / processing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage integration of food waste prevention throughout the business/supply chain (from raw material buying to marketing, logistics etc.) • Better planning/forecasting for raw material buying • Monitor, measure and report on food loss and waste quantities to identify and act on hotspots • Take full account of critical role of packaging in ensuring food quality, safety and preventing food waste • Offer consumers right portion sizes • Improve date marking practices and consumer understanding of date marking and other relevant food information jointly with other stakeholders • Where food surpluses cannot be avoided, prioritise food redistribution to humans before facilitating safe food to feed transition • Increase sales of co-products and create more innovative products that use such co-products • Increasing the diversity of market opportunities through processing • Provide on-label or on-line information to consumers about better food management

Table 15 (continued) Recommendations for Action in Food Waste Prevention Developed by the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste

Retail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish trustful relationships with suppliers and share data and forecasting information to match supply and demand • Make food waste prevention/reduction a company priority • Date marking: agree on accurate date marking to provide long shelf-life without compromising safety or quality and consider the role of innovation (e.g., bar codes) • Greater use of food repurposing in store (e.g., processing unsold fruit/vegetables) • Use consumer research to better understand causes of food waste at home and tailor products, discounts, and promotions to help consumers prevent food waste at home • Monitor, measure, and report on food waste quantities to identify and act • Put in place a favourable framework to encourage food waste reduction
Foodservice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide support to small businesses to increase their knowledge and capacity-building • Motivate and engage businesses to adopt measures against food waste in their operations • Identify solutions to the logistical challenge linked to the collection of small quantities of food in multiple locations • Monitor actions' efficiency and effectiveness by setting SMART objectives and KPI's • Help to influence consumer expectations/behaviour to reduce and prevent plate waste
Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual and community behaviour change • Develop and use a wider range of methods to better understand consumer behaviour as regards food waste and design effective solutions • Increase use and development of audience segmentation

7.3 For policy makers

The role of policy makers is to rise above the stakes of the individual stakeholders and to develop policies, guidelines and regulations that balance various societal goals. Also here, the SDGs can be taken as a reference point. We have argued in this report that FLW reduction (SDG 12.3) has direct connections with SDG2 on food security and SDG 13 on climate action.

Cattaneo et al. (2021) point out that reducing FLW may help improve supply-chain efficiency and food security but could increase CO₂ emissions from the food system, which would use more energy in cold chains. As a second example, Kuiper and Cui (2021) note that reducing food losses may lead to an “expansion effect,” which could boost economic growth and therefore induce more economy-wide GHG emissions on balance. Other trade-offs can arise if food policies to improve nutrition have the unintended effect of increasing FLW, for example, by promoting new diets that involve more nutrition-rich but also perishable fresh foods. As a final example, increased FLW may arise from inefficient and distorted food systems as an indirect consequence of agricultural subsidies. The lowered food prices may reduce incentives to avoid FLW. These examples show the importance of policy coherence across food policy domains (Cattaneo et al. 2021).

Since the food sector uses 30% of the total global energy use and accounts for 22% of the total greenhouse gas emissions⁶, the sector has a responsibility to develop effective policies to ensure that as much as possible of the produced food is consumed as intended. This is even more important because, as observed by Wang, Yuan, and Tang (2021), the amount of per capita FLW is positively correlated with per capita GDP. Economic growth, therefore, intrinsically has an exponential effect on FLW, which should be avoided by good policy.

The ZEROW project will provide concrete policy recommendations, but for now, these are out of the scope of this conceptual framework report. A separate work package (WP8) will work on these policy recommendations. We end this report by summarizing the five policy recommendations formulated by Cattaneo et al. (2021), since they illustrate the importance of a comprehensive conceptual framework for FLW:

1. Measuring and monitoring FLW
2. Assessing benefits and costs of FLW reduction and the trade-offs involved
3. Designing FLW-related policies and interventions under limited information
4. Understanding how interactions between stages along food value chain and across countries affect outcomes of FLW reduction efforts
5. Preparing for income transitions and the shifting relative importance of losses and waste as economies develop

⁶ <http://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-consumption-production/>

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Annex 1: SILL interview protocol

The SILLs descriptions and their corresponding potential additions to the conceptual model (see Section 5.2) are surveyed by means of the following interview protocol.

1. Name and email address?
2. Brief description of your SILL
3. What is the main motivation for your SILL?
 - a. Improve food security, reduce hunger
 - b. Improve business performance of food chain actors
 - c. Improve sustainability
4. Focus on food waste or food loss?
 - a. Reduce food loss
 - b. Reduce food waste
 - c. Both
5. For the impact of your SILL to be effectively measured, do you think we need to amend the available definition of FLW?
6. If FLW occurs, it can have various destinations. Which ones are most relevant for your SILL?
 - a. Animal feed
 - b. Bio-based materials/biochemical processing
 - c. Co-digestion/anaerobic digestion
 - d. Composting/aerobic processes
 - e. Controlled combustion
 - f. Land application
 - g. Landfill
 - h. Not harvested/plowed in
 - i. Refuse/discards/litter
 - j. Sewer/wastewater treatment
 - k. Foodbanks or similar
 - l. Other
7. Which parts of the Food chain does your SILL cover? More than one answer is possible.
 - a. Pre-harvest production
 - b. Harvest
 - c. Post-harvest production
 - d. Storage
 - e. Transport
 - f. Agriculture processing
 - g. Packaging
 - h. Wholesalers
 - i. Retail
 - j. Food service
 - k. Households
 - l. Return flows
 - m. Other:...
8. Which food material type does your SILL focus on?
 - a. Food only
 - b. Associated inedible parts only
 - c. Both food and associated inedible parts
9. Please indicate on which food category your SILL focuses

- a. Fruits
 - b. Vegetables
 - c. Grains
 - d. Protein Foods
 - e. Dairy
10. Please describe in words how you would scope your SILL in terms of geography. For example: local, regional, a specific country, Europe, etc.
 11. Is data availability a challenge for your SILL? (5-point Likert)
 12. Please describe how you (plan to) measure the success of your SILL? Preferably this is based on quantitative performance indicators, but qualitative ones are of course also welcome.
 13. Within which timeframe do you expect your SILL to deliver the expected results?
 - a. <6 months
 - b. 6 months - 1 year
 - c. 1-2 years
 - d. 3-4 years
 - e. 4+ years
 14. Any other comments?

Annex 2: Related European research projects

The following past or running EU funded projects provide relevant input for the ZEROW project.

CircEco – Climate Neutral Farms (ClieNFarms)

<https://digicirc.eu/circeco/>

DEMETRA - Dynamic Equilibrium Model for Economic development Resources and Agriculture

<http://demetraproject.eu/en/>

FOODRUS

<https://www.foodrus.eu/>

FUSIONS - Food Use for Social Innovation by Optimising Waste Prevention Strategies

<https://www.eu-fusions.org/>

REFRESH - Resource Efficient Food and dRink for the Entire Supply cHain

<https://www.eu-refresh.org/>

SISTERS - Systemic Innovations for a SusTainable reduction of the EuRopean food wastage

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101037796>

Annex 3: longlist measures and interventions (Diaz-Ruiz et al. 2019)

Table 16 Complete list of Food waste prevention measures, taken from (Diaz-Ruiz et al. 2019)

	#		
Primary production wholesalers	1	Agriculture planning improvement to avoid surpluses.	
	2	Forecasting farming at the cooperative level linked to produce commercialization. Promoting farmers' cooperativism organization.	
	3	Public bodies keeping track of farming forecast. Better knowledge of farmers' reality by means of audits with solution proposals.	
	4	Farmers should have the mentality of taking advantage of everything from the crop, transforming parts of the harvest that have no other way out into preserves and looking for alternative sales channels.	
	5	Guaranteeing a minimum profitable and promising price for the farmers.	
	6	Applying a flexible mechanism to prices; offering typologies according to the production volume.	
	7	Boosting a local agricultural production model.	
	8	Making the reality of primary production known to other agents in the food chain so they will be increasingly flexible in size standards.	
	9	Creating and promoting an interconnected system to redistribute and profit out of farm surpluses.	
	10	Making a plan to include food waste reduction in the management of the wholesale market, direct and indirect.	
	11	Including another category in the commercialization regulations to introduce products rejected due to aesthetic standards or sizes requirements into the market.	
Industry	12	Making efforts to improve manufacturing processes to reintegrate products within the production line.	
	13	Managing surpluses to send products that have surpassed the best before date to food banks.	
	14	Applying voluntary actions, accompanied by the administration, to reduce avoidable food waste in the food industry.	
Distribution	15	Increasing the price of industrial waste disposal management methods.	
	16	Planning together (distributors and primary producers) what is going to be consumed each season.	
	17	Industry and distributors buying whole harvest from producers and having to redistribute it to their different brand suppliers.	
	18	Redistributing food suitable for consumption but not for sale to charity canteens or social entities (food pantries) with the business' own transportation.	
	19	Training store staff about donation methods and protocols.	
	20	Developing a micro-donations program to minimize bio-waste. Donating food suitable for consumption but not for sale, according to managers, to the closest charities to the store.	
	21	Developing compulsory donation protocols for all supermarkets.	
	22	Creating a pick up route through different supermarkets from a town/city to collect food for charities, promoted and funded by the local administration.	
	23	Doing best practices guides and protocols together with the administration to guarantee food security and to minimize false myths about food donation and help store managers.	
	24	Working inside the business planning sales and logistics by working with the historic sales data and improving the adaptation of stores to clients' typology.	
	25	Different distributors and competing companies working together to find out the best ways to minimize food waste.	
	Small stores	26	Implementing campaigns aimed at buyers, together with local administrations and environmental departments to give them (buyers) anti-food waste recipes and menu planning to encourage rational purchases.
		27	Making infrastructural improvements to help with food conservation and food conservation logistics.
	Consumers	28	Working on retailers' awareness to throw away as little food as possible through stock management and the use of a cold room system.
29		Promoting a change of habits to reduce food waste volumes.	
30		Promoting food purchase planning.	
31		Developing school and school canteen teaching about food waste.	
32		Implementing a pay as you throw (PAYT) management system. Linking what we pay for waste management with the generation of waste.	
33		Supporting social movement organisations that are highlighting the problem of food waste because they are making companies and administrations react to the problem.	
34		Educating in values and valuing food and diet. Encouraging a safe and healthy diet because it creates responsibility and increases the valuation/appreciation of food.	
35		Implementing awareness campaigns to make the problem known and increase consumer concern.	
Redistribution		36	Establishing freezing protocols for fresh produce, like meat, to facilitate donation to charities.
	37	Encouraging a better knowledge of charity functioning to increase retailers and distribution companies' awareness. With trust, food redistributed increases.	
	38	Promoting the aggrupation of social entities (charities/food pantries) at the local level to join efforts and improve food redistribution.	
	39	Creating a network of potential producers and company donors of food.	
	40	Approve regulation to make the prioritisation of food redistribution over animal feed destination compulsory.	
	41	Administrative facilitation of supermarket food donation because sometimes this is bureaucratically complicated.	
	42	Increasing social pressure to increase donations.	
Along the FSC	43	Having laws to regulate the boundaries between price decreasing and donations among different actors of the supply chain.	
	44	Making legislative changes to promote food waste prevention and food redistribution.	
	45	Opening up new horizons concerning food security in such a way as to have a certain tolerance level with some products.	
	46	Incorporating laws and regulations in such a way as food donation is not depending on businessperson willingness.	
	47	Incorporating food waste prevention into waste management plans as a relevant aspect.	
	48	Promoting a strategic food access plan to ensure access to equitable food and a balanced diet for all citizens.	